

Cyber Weapons as Components of Weapon Systems

Fabrizio Baiardi, Vincenzo Sammartino

Dipartimento di Informatica, Università di Pisa, Pisa, Italy
f.baiardi@unipi.it
vincenzo.sammartino@phd.unipi.it

Research Track: CSCI-RTCW: Cyber Warfare, Cyber Defense, & Cyber Security

Abstract. The potential weaknesses of cyber weapons, such as their fragility or manipulations to circumvent their functions, may be overcome by viewing them as components of a weapon system. The main component of this system is the attack infrastructure that supports the interaction of the attackers with the weapons. The critical role of the infrastructure is confirmed by experience with malware strains and their evolutions, where the attack infrastructure mitigates vulnerabilities in these strains. In the case of weapons, the infrastructure enables the attacker to coordinate and update the various modules of the weapon, even after deploying the weapon on target systems or when it spreads in the internet to reach these targets. Adopting this infrastructure is aligned with other physical weapons because they are also elements of a weapon system. We also discuss the modules that define a weapon and alternative designs for a weapon.

Keywords: Cyber weapon · Payload · Attack infrastructure · Spread · Deployment · One-to-many weapon.

1 Introduction

Several researchers have investigated the topic of cyber weapons and discussed their effectiveness. This effectiveness is crucial because these weapons exploit specific vulnerabilities to spread in computer networks and persist in target systems. Still a weapon becomes ineffectual once the owners of the target systems address the vulnerabilities it exploits. This is the reason why some researchers describe a cyber weapon as single-use because its usage reveals the vulnerabilities it exploits, which leads to their remediation. Similar reasoning explains someone defines cyber weapons as fragile because a new release of the target systems may make them ineffective [1,9,16,19,22,21,29,32,36]. These conclusions focus too much on a single component of a cyber weapon, namely its payload. Distinct conclusions are reached if we see the payload as just one module of a weapon system with other components, such as a diffusion vector and the attack infrastructure. This infrastructure enables interactions with a weapon [11,28] to

update the payload and other modules to preserve effectiveness despite remediation of the vulnerabilities that current versions of weapon modules exploit. Furthermore, the time to produce and apply a patch, the most common remediation, is measured in days, if not weeks, while new versions of a weapon may be generated quickly and employed against various targets within a brief timeframe, rendering comprehensive mitigation for all the targets impractical. Lastly, even a single use cyber weapon may hit a large, or even a huge, number of targets by implementing a one-to-many attack [2].

Fig. 1. Glossary of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
cw	a cyber weapon
Ij(cw)	one instance, i.e. a copy of cw
A(cw)	the actor, i.e. a state, that has produced cw
At(A(cw))	the attack infrastructure to interact with the instances of cw
AutCt(cw)	the module that discovers a node is a target
C2(cw)	the module to interact with the infrastructure and download new versions
Di(cw)	the module to spread cw in a network to reach its targets
Pay(cw)	the payload module of cw that is executed to produce the impact
Pe(cw)	the module that escalates the privileges to install modules on a target
Sp(cw)	the module to spread instances of cw in a network to reach its targets
T(cw)	the targets of cw, where to install and execute the payload
tde(cw)	the starting time of the design of cw
tdp(cw)	the time when cw is available, i.e. it has been designed and implemented
tf(cw)	the time when the execution of Pay(cw) can be fired

From our perspective, a cyber weapon is a complex, modular system. The main element of this system is an attack infrastructure. This is a botnet that connects network nodes the attacker controls and uses to stealthily interact with the cyber weapons it has deployed. Sophisticated attack infrastructures integrate secure communication channels, fail-safe protocols, and evasion methods to maintain continuous access to certain nodes while avoiding detection by security monitoring systems [11,13,15,17,27]. The attack infrastructure supports the spreading of the weapon’s instances, each including a payload. Instances spread by navigating across network nodes until some instances successfully infect and persist on some nodes, the targets of the weapon. The attacker then uses the infrastructure to interact with these instances to choose if and when to activate the payload and produce effects, such as collecting and exfiltrating data, destroying systems, and overwriting or corrupting data. The overall impact depends on whether the targets are cyber or cyber-physical systems [34]. The view of a cyber weapon as part of a weapon system aligns with the knowledge we have gained from the different malware strains, their development, and updates. This confirms the critical role of the attack infrastructure in the production and deployment of variants of malware.

This paper proceeds as follows. Sect. 2 discusses the adoption of an attack infrastructure, while Sect. 3 outlines the modular structure of a cyber weapon and

the role of each modules. Then, Sect.4 describes the design space of a weapon, while Sect. 5 considers some attributes of a cyber weapon. Sect. 6 investigates alternative compromises among contrasting requirements. Figure 1 resumes the abbreviations we use.

1.1 Our contribution

The primary contribution of this paper lies in the examination of matters pertinent to the creation and dissemination of a cyber weapon, by treating it as a modular component within a weapons system. We show that the effectiveness and fragility of cyber weapons can be addressed if the weapon payload is just one module of a system built around an attack infrastructure. This infrastructure can replace and improve this module, as well as other ones, after its deployment on targets and before its execution.

2 The Attack Infrastructure of a Cyber Weapon

This section discusses the role of the attack infrastructure in a general scenario, where a lethal autonomous weapon system (laws) [20,28] that is introduced into a network, usually the Internet, and navigates through it to reach its targets. We consider strategic cyber weapons with an impact far from the battlefield against the critical infrastructures of a nation. In the following, we assume that strategies of cybercrime gangs can also be applied to a cyber weapon. This assumption is based on the tight relations between these gangs and state-sponsored operators [8,24]. Several pieces of evidence support this assumption. As an example, several countries have most frequently drawn on resources from criminal forums. We consider strategic cyber weapons with an impact far from the battlefield against national critical infrastructures.

Fig. 2. Spreading of a cyber weapon in a network.

2.1 A weapon and its attack infrastructure

A cyber weapon cw is an integrated set of modules that an adversary $A(cw)$ builds to manipulate some ICT/OT systems, $T(cw)$, the targets of cw . The number and the kinds of modules in $T(cw)$ determine the impact of cw while the existence of several targets stresses the one-to-many nature of cyber weapons because a single weapon usually hits a set of targets in a coordinated manner. The impact of cw may be limited to the cyber world, i.e. a wiper that erases documents and databases, or it may also affect the physical world, i.e. a malware to manipulate an industrial control system to destroy it [34]. The size of $T(cw)$ may be initially unknown and be determined according to attributes of the network nodes that cw crosses when spreading, i.e. according to the applications they run.

In general, at any moment after starting the spreading of cw by deploying it on a network node, several instances, i.e. copies, of cw spread in the network to reach their targets. An instance of cw running on a node $N1$ moves to node $N2$ by executing a remote attack from $N1$ to $N2$. If the attack is successful, the instance on $N1$ creates a copy of itself on $N2$. An instance attacks several nodes each time there is a fork in the paths it can follow, and it forks a new instance on each node it has successfully attacked. This implies that at any moment, n instances $I1(cw), \dots, In(cw)$ of cw may run in parallel on distinct nodes. $A(cw)$ can set or not an upper bound for n a priori. Usually, no bound is set when $A(cw)$ cannot access accurate information on $T(cw)$ or on the paths to reach these targets. Anyway, to minimise both effort and noise, $A(cw)$ can insert some controls in cw to avoid repeating attacks against a node it has already reached. If the controls are effective, each node executes at most one instance of cw . In the example in Figure 2, an instance in $N1$ creates two instances after attacking $N2$ and $N3$, while the instance in $N4$ creates instances on $N5$ and $N6$.

Fig. 3. An attack infrastructure (Bot nodes) that Interfaces $A(cw)$ (Botmaster) with the nodes where cw has been installed or with those it crosses in its spreading (Victim)

We assume that $A(cw)$ has built and uses an attack infrastructure $At(A(cw))$, see Figure 3, to interact with the instances $I1(cw), \dots, In(cw)$. This transforms

cw into an element of a weapon system. $At(A(cw))$ usually consists of a botnet of nodes with distinct owners. $A(cw)$ controls these nodes because it has previously attacked them to install tools that support stealth interactions between $A(w)$ and $I1(cw), \dots, In(cw)$ to exchange information, update their modules and coordinate their operations. $At(A(cw))$ hides $A(cw)$ behind nodes controlled by other organisations to obfuscate, e.g. increase the complexity of, attribution of cw . However, $At(A(cw))$ may exist even when obfuscation is useless, because its main role is to enable the interactions between $A(cw)$ and $I1(cw), \dots, In(cw)$ [6]. Several weapons built by $A(cw)$ usually share, at least partially, the same attack infrastructure. The diamond model of cyber intrusions [4] confirms the role of $At(A(cw))$ as one of the four core features of any cyber intrusion: adversary, infrastructure, capability, and victim. Most of the infrastructures that threat actors use to interact with malware or ransomware they deploy include legitimate Internet services such as Telegram, GitHub, or OneDrive [12,15,17,18,23,27,33]. This blends the traffic of $At(A(cw))$ with the normal one as a first countermeasure against the discovery and seizure of domains and servers in $At(A(cw))$. Even if command and control communications in these legitimate services are seldom advanced and rarely sophisticated, this strategy adds a layer of complexity for defenders as it increases the risk of misidentifying malicious activity as legitimate.

3 Modules of a cyber weapon

We discuss a modular decomposition of a weapon and point out how an attack infrastructure can support and simplify these modules. Simpler weapons will be discussed as well. The decomposition we propose is consistent with the seven stages of the Lockheed-Martin cyber-kill chain [14]. It also is consistent with the defining characteristics of cyber weapons [36].

We extend [10] by functionally decomposing cw into four modules:

1. Command and control, $C2(cw)$.
2. Spreading, $Sp(w)$.
3. Persistence, $Pe(cw)$.
4. Payload, $Pay(cw)$.

Each module can be further decomposed into simpler ones to increase flexibility and software reuse. Our decomposition also supports the definition of the four important features of a cyber weapon, which are:

- a) The role of $At(A(cw))$.
- b) How cw spreads.
- c) How cw persists in its target.
- d) The payload of cw .

In the following, we show how $At(A(cw))$ can tune and update the last features.

Command & control module $C2(cw)$ interacts with $A(cw)$ through $At(A(cw))$ to exchange information and to download and install updated versions for any module of cw . $C2(cw)$ communicates to $A(cw)$ information on any node where an instance is running as soon as the instance is created. In general, the communications are encrypted to preserve integrity and confidentiality.

Spreading $Sp(cw)$ has to spread cw across the Internet to reach its targets. It can be further decomposed into two modules:

1. Diffusion module $Di(cw)$,
2. Autonomous control module $AutCt(cw)$.

$Di(cw)$ attacks another node to generate another instance of cw on the target. It typically exploits one or several vulnerabilities that grant remote code execution on the target. They are classified as wormable, referring to malware that replicates itself on other nodes. Any new instance of cw includes all its modules. To avoid an uncontrolled spreading, $Di(cw)$ may even destroy, ie kill, an instance that has not yet reached a target at the end of a time interval. This event may also be fired by commands from $A(cw)$ through $At(A(cw))$.

When $Di(cw)$ creates a new instance of cw on a node, it activates $AutCt(cw)$. $AutCt(cw)$ decides if the underlying node belongs to $T(cw)$ and, if so, it activates $Pe(cw)$. Then, it activates $Di(cw)$ to spread cw to other nodes. The simplest version of $AutCt(cw)$ collects data on the underlying node and transmits it to $At(A(cw))$, where the decision is taken. Other versions may use more sophisticated or even AI strategies [26,29,30], but simpler strategies to discover targets have been used successfully for a long time.

In the spreading example in Figure 2, an instance of cw is forked on $N1$ through an Internet connection. This instance attacks both $N2$ and $N3$ and creates one instance on each of these nodes. Both instances spread autonomously. As an example, if all the remote attacks are successful, the instance running on $N2$ creates two instances on $N4$ and $N6$ while the one on $N4$ creates two instances on, respectively, $N5$ and $N5$. If one instance in Figure 2 runs on a node with an Internet connection, it can use it to spread to other networks.

$Di(cw)$ and $AutCt(cw)$ cooperate because $Di(cw)$ tries to spread instances of cw on any network node, while $AutCt(cw)$ prunes instances on nodes that do not belong to $T(cw)$. cw uses these nodes just as stepping stones to its targets. Further mechanisms to prevent an out-of-control spread of cw are:

1. Each instance is paired with a counter and spreads only if it is positive. Any time it creates another instance, it decreases the counter and pairs with the new instance.
2. $Di(cw)$ never attacks nodes with an IP address in a predefined set.
3. $AutC(cw)$ never activates the persistence module on nodes with some features, i.e. on nodes with a keyboard with a given alphabet.

Persistence $Pe(cw)$ installs $C2(cw)$, $AutC(cw)$, and $Di(cw)$ at each node that cw crosses as it spreads. Instead, it installs $Pay(cw)$ only if $AutC(cw)$ recognizes the node as a target. If this requires additional privileges, $Pe(cw)$ implements the corresponding escalation. Some weapons do not include $Pe(cw)$ because $AutC(cw)$ immediately fires the execution of $Pay(cw)$. New versions of $Pe(cw)$ that $A(cw)$ downloads through $At(A(cw))$ may exploit new vulnerabilities. In this way, cw takes advantage of the time between the discovery and the patching of a vulnerability.

Payload Either $Pe(cw)$ immediately runs $Pay(cw)$ after implementing the proper attack chain, or it stealthily installs both $Pay(cw)$ and $C2(cw)$. After being installed, $Pay(cw)$ can interact through $At(A(cw))$ with $A(cw)$. This enables the update of $Pay(cw)$ to enrich the vulnerabilities it can exploit as well as to synchronize the execution of payloads on distinct targets. This is related to the one-to-many feature of cw , and it may be fundamental to achieving the overall impact of interest. Maximum flexibility is achieved when $Pay(cw)$ acts as a beacon that transmits information on the target node to $A(cw)$ that then selects the best payload to install.

Dependencies among modules The modules of cw are largely independent, as new versions of each one can be developed and implemented separately. Furthermore, the vulnerabilities that $Sp(cw)$ exploits to spread cw are independent of those that $Pay(cw)$ exploits to produce an impact. This implies that some modules of a weapon may have already been developed or that a module can be developed in parallel with the payload. This is a fundamental advantage that $At(A(cw))$ offers.

Features of a cyber weapon According to [34], the four features of a cyber weapon are:

1. They may combine multiple payloads for espionage, data theft, or sabotage.
2. A stealth capability to persist within the targets over an extended period.
3. A detailed knowledge of the workings of the targets.
4. Proper code to bypass security controls.

We notice that both the ability to combine multiple payloads and the capability of persisting within the target are strongly related to the availability of an attack infrastructure to interact with the instances of $Pay(cw)$ that have been installed. Distinct payloads result from merging various functions in $Pay(cw)$ and then coordinating them via $At(A(cw))$. The stealth capability of spreading and achieving persistence is delegated to $Di(cw)$ and $Pe(cw)$ but $A(cw)$ can update these modules using $At(Cw)$ to preserve their effectiveness in spite of updates to the target infrastructure.

The attack infrastructure also supports the collection of information on the working on the target and on its security controls to update the various modules of cw .

4 Design Space and Practical Examples

The design and deployment strategies for a cyber weapon vary significantly based on the attacker's objectives, context, and resources. The following well-known examples show alternative implementations of weapons, linking them to the modular concepts and strategies discussed.

4.1 Simplest Weapons and Physical Delivery

The most basic cyber weapons are simple payloads delivered physically to a target system. The most famous example is **Stuxnet**, which was initially introduced into the air-gapped network of the Iranian nuclear facility at Natanz via an infected USB flash drive. Such weapons may consist almost exclusively of a persistence module ($\text{Pe}(\text{cw})$) and the payload ($\text{Pay}(\text{cw})$). This avoids the adoption of the spreading module ($\text{Sp}(\text{cw})$) to reach the targets.

4.2 Spreading through Manual Intrusions

An alternative to both spreading and physical delivery is the deployment by human operators through a series of intrusions. This method was used to deploy the **LockerGaga** ransomware in the 2019 attack against the aluminum giant Norsk Hydro [31,34]. The attackers first gained access to the network and then used legitimate administrative tools to distribute the malware to critical systems. This technique is known as "living off the land". This solution is often favoured by actors targeting critical infrastructure, as it allows for precise control and the pre-positioning of capabilities for future use.

4.3 Spreading through the Supply Chain

A highly effective method involves injecting the weapon into a trusted software supply chain [7]. The **SolarWinds** attack is a prime example: attackers compromised the build process of the Orion software, inserting a backdoor into updates that were then distributed to thousands of customers. Similarly, a backdoor discovered in **Magento** plugins lay dormant for six years before being activated to attack 11,000 online stores [5]. In these scenarios, the command and control module ($\text{C2}(\text{cw})$) is crucial, allowing the attacker to interact with the vast base of infections, identify which are the targets of real interest, and selectively activate the payload.

4.4 Late Payload Download and "Weapon-as-a-Service"

To accelerate deployment and increase flexibility, an attacker can spread a version of cw that lacks $\text{Pay}(\text{cw})$. Once cw reaches a target, $\text{C2}(\text{cw})$ contacts the attack infrastructure to download and install the most appropriate payload. The **Emotet** botnet is a key example of this strategy. Originally a banking trojan, it evolved into a delivery infrastructure for other malware, such as the Ryuk ransomware. The actual payload was downloaded only after the infection was established, effectively enabling a "weapon-as-a-service" model.

4.5 Mass Weapons and Indiscriminate Impact

Some weapons are designed for mass impact, attacking every node they can infect. Wipers are a clear example. The **NotPetya** malware, disguised as ransomware, was in fact a destructive wiper that spread uncontrollably on a global scale, causing billions of dollars in damage after initially targeting Ukrainian organizations. These weapons typically lack $\text{AutCt}(cw)$ and they install the payload on every system they can compromise, thereby maximizing destruction or disruption.

5 Attributes of Cyber Weapons

The effectiveness, cost, and overall impact of cyber weapons are primarily determined by their attributes, which are influenced by the capabilities of $\text{At}(A(cw))$. These attributes include power, impact, fragility, latency, development time, control, autonomy, robustness, and the role of attack infrastructure.

5.1 Power and impact

The power, or intensity [35], of cw is evaluated by the number of its targets where it has installed $\text{Pay}(cw)$. The ratio between this number and the size of $\text{T}(cw)$ is a simple assessment of the power at a given time and it depends upon the number of vulnerabilities that $\text{Di}(cw)$ and $\text{Pe}(cw)$ can exploit, respectively, to spread cw and install $\text{Pay}(cw)$ on a target node. $A(cw)$ can measure the current power of cw if $\text{C2}(cw)$ is installed not only on the nodes in $\text{T}(cw)$ but also on any node where cw spreads and informs $A(cw)$ about the deployment. If $A(cw)$ believes that the current power is too low, it can download new versions of $\text{Di}(cw)$ and/or $\text{Pe}(cw)$. This flexibility is paid for by interactions through $\text{Att}(A(cw))$ that increase the probability of detecting the spreading. We distinguish the power of cw from its impact because this depends mainly upon the kind of systems in $\text{T}(cw)$. As an example, if $\text{Pay}(cw)$ manipulates some databases that drive the behaviour of an industrial control system, we can expect a larger impact than when the databases are those of an e-commerce site.

5.2 Fragility

Any assessment of fragility of cw should consider that the adoption of both $\text{At}(A(cw))$ and $\text{C2}(w)$ enable $A(cw)$ to update $\text{Sp}(cw)$, $\text{Pe}(cw)$ and $\text{Pay}(cw)$. Hence, $A(cw)$ may produce and install new versions of these modules to remove some bugs or to take advantage of newly discovered vulnerabilities. Furthermore, $A(cw)$ can choose new targets for some or all the instances. Hence, while each version of cw is fragile, the overall weapon may be highly robust due to updates through $\text{At}(A(cw))$. This stresses the importance of $\text{At}(A(cw))$ and the view of cw as just one module of a weapon system. It also shows that the fragility of cyber weapons is strongly influenced not only by the capability of the defenders but also by the ability to interact with weapons after they have been deployed.

The critical role of the infrastructure is confirmed by available data on the most effective malware. As an example, Emotet first appeared in 2014 as a banking trojan, and it has evolved into one of the largest malware-as-a-service infrastructures [3,35]. The threat actors behind Emotet implemented a series of attack waves that delivered a variety of different payloads, including IcedID, TrickBot, UmbreCrypt and QakBot. Emotet was active until January 2021 when law enforcement targeted its attack infrastructure in a coordinated takedown effort, Operation Ladybird. The malware had a comeback in 2022 before its definitive end. Three main variants of Emotet and several minor ones have been deployed that used more than twenty attack techniques [25]. The prolonged persistence of successive malware versions confirms the potential robustness of a cyber weapon when we see Emotet not as a malware but as a weapon that has been spread eight years before its activation, properly maintained and updated through an attack infrastructure

5.3 Latency

Latency affects the effectiveness of cw if the size and the elements in $T(cw)$ are decided in advance, and it strongly depends upon the number of vulnerabilities that $Sp(cw)$ can exploit. To minimise latency, these vulnerabilities should be highly heterogeneous and affect distinct operating systems and applications [26] as this enables cw to spread through interconnected networks and to exploit any available path to reach a target. Latency is most critical when the execution of $Pay(cw)$ is synchronised in all the targets because it is given by the longest time to reach a target. Anyway, the time to patch all the systems to stop the spreading of cw is usually several orders of magnitude larger than the latency provided that both the spreading can reach all the targets and the vulnerabilities that $Sp(cw)$ can exploit suffice to reach these targets.

5.4 Time to develop

This time is given by $tdp(cw)-tde(cw)$. In principle, $Pay(Cw)$ and $AutCt(w)$ are the only modules to be developed to build a new weapon. Even $Pe(cw)$ is developed if cw is the first weapon of $A(cw)$ that exploits the corresponding attack chain. We believe that this is a minor case due to the large homogeneity in ICT networks and nodes. Any other cw module from a previous weapon can be reused. The time to develop $Pay(Cw)$ is related to the power of cw and to the number of vulnerabilities to exploit. If $A(cw)$ has a bag of exploits available, the development time is determined by the number of exploits that $A(cw)$ can use. The time strongly increases if no exploit is available or if new vulnerabilities are needed to spread or install the payload. The time to develop $AutCt(cw)$ mostly depends on the one to define a “signature” of $T(cw)$ namely a compact representation of the features of all and only the nodes in $T(cw)$. This definition may involve new intrusions to collect data or the exfiltration of data from previous intrusions. The attack infrastructure strongly reduces the time to collect this data. Furthermore, latency can be reduced by spreading cw

from distinct nodes of $At(A(cw))$ in parallel. We have already discussed how to reduce the time to develop by spreading a version of cw without $Pay(cw)$ or it is a simple loader to install $Pay(cw)$.

5.5 Control and autonomy

The first attribute assesses the control of $A(cw)$ on the spreading of cw and the triggering of $Pay(cw)$. It may be approximated as the probability that only the nodes in $T(cw)$ are influenced by the execution of $Pay(cw)$ when and if it is fired. The autonomy of cw depends both upon its ability to spread to nodes in $T(cw)$ and to identify nodes in $T(cw)$ without any interaction with $A(cw)$. Full autonomy requires the gathering of a large amount of data to develop and debug the two modules in $Sp(cw)$ because cw cannot interact through $At(cw)$. Instead, if both $AutCt(cw)$ and $C2(cw)$ are installed, $AutCt(cw)$ can, at run time, gather data on the node where it is running and send it to $At(cw)$, which checks if the node is a target. This overlaps the spreading of cw with the collection of information to discover nodes in $T(cw)$ and their signature. Further controls in $AutC(cw)$ can prevent spreading to some IP addresses and some geographical regions.

5.6 Robustness

This attribute assesses the complexity for the owner of the nodes in $T(cw)$ of subverting the behaviour of cw to utilise it against $A(cw)$. Since cw is highly complex, there will be some vulnerabilities in some of its modules. This may lead to the discovery of the spreading of cw , the capture of some instances and their reverse engineering to convert cw into a weapon to be launched against those who created it. Strategies to slow down the reverse engineering of cw include obfuscation and polymorphism of the code of cw [6]. $At(A(cw))$ affects this attribute too because the time to subvert the behaviour of cw mainly depends upon the spreading time, and the attack infrastructure can reduce this time.

5.7 Attributes and the attack infrastructure

Currently, the primary decision in the design of a cyber weapon concerns whether to use autonomous spreading or intrusions from nodes of $At(A(cw))$. Autonomous spreading will become a viable option in the future, but currently, a set of intrusions is the preferred approach, at least to speed up the spreading, and each intrusion may be automated through an attack platform. Autonomous spreading may require some compromises. As an example, the time to install cw on its targets, namely the sum of $tdp(cw)$, when the spreading starts and the latency, can be reduced by approximating the signature to collect less data. This compromise is one of the reasons for the trilemma [19], but multiple factors determine the intensity of cw , including its fragility, rather than the latency and the time for its development only. In any case, the attack infrastructure simplifies and speed

up the spreading and the deployment. In general, $A(cw)$ does not dynamically produce cw when it needs but produces it in advance together with $At(A(cw))$.

Malware strains, i.e. variants, are an important example of how an attack infrastructure can increase the effectiveness of cw by providing additional computing power and more precise information about targets as well as alternative versions of modules to download. This is also confirmed by the continuous evolution of techniques to build these infrastructures and to minimise the probability that they are detected. As an example, the attack infrastructures of several APT groups are operational relay boxes, orb, networks [17,23]. These are botnets that consist of virtual private servers together with compromised Internet of Things devices, smart devices, and routers. Most of these nodes are end-of-life or unsupported by their manufacturers. In this way, the attackers can grow the size of the infrastructure with little effort to create a constantly evolving network.

6 Conclusion

Our main conclusion is that an attack infrastructure can remediate most weaknesses of a cyber weapon, as it supports the deployment of new versions of a weapon. An analysis of attack tactics, techniques, and procedures by criminal gangs and malware developers confirms the importance of this infrastructure. A prerequisite for creating such an infrastructure is the ability to persist stealthily within adversary networks. This is confirmed by the wide adoption of living-off-the-land techniques in intrusions because subverting the behaviour of tools already installed on the target system, rather than downloading new ones, minimises the likelihood of detection. A second conclusion is the importance of dismantling the attack infrastructures of potential adversaries as a preliminary step to defend against cyber weapons.

References

1. Axelrod, R., Iliev, R.: Timing of cyber conflict. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences **111**(4), 1298–1303 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1322638111>
2. Boschetti, N., Gordon, N, G., Falco, G.: Space cybersecurity lessons learned from the viasat cyberattack. In: ASCEND 2022. p. 4380 (2022)
3. Boyarchuk, O., Mariani, S., Ortolani, S., Vigna, G.: Keeping up with the emotets: Tracking a multi-infrastructure botnet. Digital Threats: Research and Practice **4**(3), 41 (2023)
4. Caltagirone, S., Pendergast, A., Betz, C.: The diamond model of intrusion analysis. Tech. rep., Threat Connect (2013)
5. Cimpanu, C.: Risky bulletin: Six-years-old backdoor comes to life to hijack magento stores. <https://risky.biz/risky-bulletin-six-years-old-backdoor-comes-to-life-to-hijack-magento-stores/> (2025)
6. Ebad, A., Darem, A., Abawajy, J, H.: Measuring software obfuscation quality—a systematic literature review. IEEE Access **9**, 99024–99038 (2021)

7. Ghanbari, H., Koskinen, K., Wei, Y.: From solarwinds to kaseya: The rise of supply chain attacks in a digital world. *Journal of Information Technology Teaching Cases* (2024)
8. Google Threat Intelligence Group: Cybercrime: A multifaceted national security threat. <https://cloud.google.com/blog/topics/threat-intelligence/cybercrime-multifaceted-national-security-threat> (2025)
9. Healey, J.: Cyber operations and maschmeyer’s “subversion trilemma”. *Lawfare*, <https://www.lawfaremedia.org/article/cyber-operations-and-maschmeyers-subversion-trilemma> (2022)
10. Herr, T.: Prep: A framework for malware & cyber weapons. *Journal of Information Warfare* **13**(1), 87–106 (2014)
11. Huskaj, H, G., Iftimie, Ion, A., Wilson, R, L.: Designing attack infrastructure for offensive cyberspace operations. In: *European Conference on Information Warfare and Security, ECCWS* (2020)
12. Insikt Group: Threat actors leverage internet services to enhance data theft and weaken security defenses. Tech. rep. (2023)
13. Insikt Group: 2024 malicious infrastructure report. Tech. rep. (2025)
14. Kareem, K., et al.: Understanding the defence of operational technology (ot) systems: A comparison of lockheed martin’s cyber kill chain, mitre att&ck framework, and diamond model. In: *The International Conference on Computing, Communication, Cybersecurity & AI*. Springer Nature Switzerland (2024)
15. Khattak, S., et al.: A taxonomy of botnet behavior, detection, and defense. *IEEE communications surveys & tutorials* **16**(2), 898–924 (2013)
16. Libicki, M.C.: Cyberspace is not a warfighting domain. *A Journal of Law and Policy for the Information Society* **8**(2), 326 (2012)
17. Mandiant: The gru’s destructive playbook. Tech. rep. (2023)
18. Mandiant: Ioc extinction? china-nexus cyber espionage actors use orb networks to raise cost on defenders. Tech. rep. (May 2024)
19. Maschmeyer, L.: The subversive trilemma: Why cyber operations fall short of expectations. *International Security* **46**(2), 51–90 (2021). https://doi.org/10.1162/isec_a_00418
20. Maschmeyer, L.: Subverting skynet: The strategic promise of lethal autonomous weapons and the perils of exploitation. In: *14th International Conference on Cyber Conflict: Keep Moving! (CyCon)*. pp. 155–171. Tallinn, Estonia (2022). <https://doi.org/10.23919/CyCon55549.2022.9811008>
21. Maschmeyer, L.: *Subversion: From Covert Operations to Cyber Conflict*. Oxford University Press (2024)
22. Maschmeyer, L., Cavely, M.D.: Goodbye cyberwar: Ukraine as reality check. Tech. Rep. 3, *CSS Policy Perspectives* (2022)
23. McEvoy, T.R., Wolthusen, S.D.: Paying the rent: A formal methods riposte to “living off the land” attacks. In: Oliva, G., Panzieri, S., Hämmerli, B., Pascucci, F., Faramondi, L. (eds.) *Critical Information Infrastructures Security. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol. 15549. Springer (2024). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-84260-3_6
24. Milenkoski, A., Minier, J., Vögele, J, F., Smeets, M., Grossman, T.: Ransomware’s new masters: How states are hijacking cybercrime. Tech. rep., *Pharos Report No. 3, Virtual Routes* (2025)
25. MITRE: Emotet. <https://attack.mitre.org/software/S0367/>
26. Nguyen D, D, A., Alain, P., Autrel, F., Bouabdallah, A., J, F., G, D.: How fast does malware leveraging eternalblue propagate? the case of wannacry and notpetya.

- In: IEEE 10th International Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft). pp. 399–404. Saint Louis, MO, USA (2024)
27. Rai, R.: Behavioural threat detection: Detecting living of land techniques. <http://essay.utwente.nl/83610/> (2020)
 28. Reinhold, T., Reuter, C.: Toward a cyber weapons assessment model—assessment of the technical features of malicious software. *IEEE Transactions on Technology and Society* **3**(3), 226–239 (2022)
 29. Rid, T.: Cyber war will not take place. *Journal of Strategic Studies* **35**(1), 5–32 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1080/01402390.2011.608939>
 30. Rodriguez, M., et al.: A framework for evaluating emerging cyberattack capabilities of ai. arXiv preprint arXiv:2503.11917 (2025)
 31. Slovik, J.: Spyware stealer locker wiper. lockergaga revisited. Tech. rep., Dragos Inc. (2020)
 32. Smeets, M.: A matter of time: On the transitory nature of cyberweapons. *Journal of Strategic Studies* **41**(1–2), 6–32 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1080/01402390.2017.1288107>
 33. Talib, M, A., Nasir, Q., Nassif, A, B., Mokhamed, T., et al.: Apt beaconing detection: A systematic review. *Computers & Security* **122**, 102875 (2022)
 34. Vatsyayan, V., et al.: A detailed investigation of popular attacks on cyber physical systems. In: *Cyber Security Applications for Industry 4.0*. Chapman and Hall/CRC (2022)
 35. VMware Threat Analysis Unit: Emotet exposed: A look inside the cybercriminal supply chain. Tech. rep. (2022)
 36. Wilson, C.: Cyber weapons: 4 defining characteristics. GCN.com, <https://www.route-fifty.com/cybersecurity/2015/06/cyber-weapons-4-defining-characteristics/287193/> (2015)